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INNOVATIVE LDF™ THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments of the innovative LDF™ thermoplastic composites technology are reviewed with emphasis on discussion of the technology fundamental basis and composites property performance. The proprietary technology employs reinforcement of long, aligned discontinuous fibers including carbon, Kevlar® or glass with an average length of 5 cm or longer in combination with a thermoplastic matrix (PEKK) in composites. Fabrication processes such as stretch forming and press forming can be employed in fabrication of LDF™ composite parts.

The LDF™ composites technology is cost effective for manufacturing complex shape parts of aerospace structures. LDF™ composites show excellent mechanical properties comparable to that of the continuous fiber reinforced counterpart, since the reinforcing long fibers with thermoplastic matrix are well aligned. Mechanical test results with various LDF™ composites confirm the fundamental theory for non-continuous fiber reinforcement describing critical fiber length necessary to achieve efficient average stress transfer in a composite.

The mechanical and other relevant property data are presented and discussed for performance comparison of LDF™ AS-4/PEKK composite material systems relative to the matched continuous fiber reinforced composites. Potential application of LDF™ thermoplastic composites technology for high performance aerospace structural parts are discussed with demonstration of thermoplastic wing ribs fabricated for a tiltrotor aircraft.

KEYWORDS: LDF™ Technology; Thermoplastic Composites; Mechanical Properties; Elastic-plastic Properties; Thermal Properties; Creep; Fatigue; Carbon Fiber Composites; Kevlar® Aramid Composites; Poly(ether ketone ketone).

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past couple of years the focus in advanced composite technology has been to reduce the cost of maintaining and acquiring composite structures while retaining the performance advantage over metals. The composite industry has responded to this challenge by developing toughened resin systems, textile preforms and automated fabrication processes to achieve these goals. Recent Air Force sponsored studies on thermoplastic composite structures have begun to verify the improved damage resistance of tough thermoplastic resin based composite systems which have the potential for lower maintenance costs [1]. In the area of lower acquisition costs for composite structures, efforts are currently being expended to combine innovative material forms with automated processes to substantially reduce the labor involved in making composite structures. Examples of automated processes being evaluated are resin transfer molding of braided materials and thermoforming. Thermoforming of thermoplastic matrix composites is analogous to low cost metal forming processes such as sheet stamping [2, 3]. Fabrication of simple curvature structures using these processes have been demonstrated with continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites, yet, wrinkle free complex shape structures have been elusive due to the lack of ductility of the material created by the inextensibility of the continuous fibers.

Aligned, discontinuous fiber materials such as that used in LDF™ technology provide a "drawable" feature to the material which can overcome some of the thermoforming limitations encountered with continuous fiber systems. While aligned, discontinuous fiber systems offer the benefits of a more "processable" system, there are concerns about the effect of the fiber ends on the static mechanical, dynamic, and environmental performance of these systems. This paper is an overview of the performance aspect of aligned, discontinuous fiber systems with a high performance thermoplastic matrix poly(ether ketone ketone) (PEKK) [4] used in LDF™ Technology. Dynamic and static mechanical properties will be presented and compared to the analogous continuous fiber reinforced composite to determine the effect of the discontinuous fibers. A brief review of the fundamental theory for discontinuous fiber reinforced composites will be made and shown to be in agreement with the results of this study.

2. TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

A key feature in Du Pont's aligned, discontinuous fiber systems is the ability to provide cost effective fabrication processes without loss of structural properties when compared to continuous fiber systems. To understand how such performances can be obtained from a discontinuous fiber system, it is helpful to examine theories on stress transfer [5].

The most often quoted theory is shear-lag analysis where the stress distribution along the length of a fiber can be understood by considering the equilibrium forces on a small element of fiber embedded in resin. In this model, the rate of increase of fiber stress is proportional to the shear stress at the interface. A critical fiber length, L_c , is defined as the minimum fiber length in which the maximum allowable fiber stress (fiber ultimate strength) can be achieved at the fiber mid point. The relationship calculating the critical fiber length is given by:

$$L_c = \frac{\sigma d}{2 s}$$

where

- L_c = critical fiber length
- σ = maximum tensile stress
- d = fiber diameter
- s = fiber/matrix shear strength

Ideally, the highest performance a composite can attain is when the average fiber stress integrated over the fiber length is equal to the ultimate fiber strength. Maximum fiber reinforcement efficiency is mathematically achieved when the fiber length exceeds 50 times the critical fiber length.

Assuming that the interfacial shear strength can be approximated by the measured short beam shear strength values, the critical fiber length for the AS-4 carbon/PEKK and Kevlar® 49 aramid/PEKK composite systems are estimated to be 0.012 cm and 0.039 cm, respectively [6, 7]. The average fiber length of these LDF™ systems (5.6 cm, 9.7 cm respectively) easily exceeds fifty times the estimated critical fiber length. This would suggest that continuous fiber composite mechanical performance should be attained provided equivalent fiber orientation can be achieved and that the fiber ends are randomly distributed throughout the composite (i.e. no high number density regions of fiber ends where premature failure could initiate). Previous published data [6] in fiber alignment characterization indicates similar orientation between the LDF™ system and continuous fiber system. Thus, the mechanical performance of the LDF™ system would be predicted to be similar to its continuous fiber analog based on its fiber length and alignment.

3. CHARACTERIZATION OF ELASTIC-PLASTIC BEHAVIORS

3.1 Characterization Studies

The elastic and plastic behaviors of LDFTM AS-4/PEKK versus its counterpart of continuous fiber reinforced composites were characterized at room and elevated temperatures up to 177°C [8]. Off-axis coupon specimens were used to generate stress-strain curves from which the elastic-plastic properties were extracted. A one parameter plastic function previously developed by Sun and Chen [9] was employed to model the elastic-plastic behaviors of both LDFTM and continuous fiber composites at room and elevated temperatures. It is expected that this study will provide structural analysts and designers an efficient tool in stress analysis and hence expedite wide applications of LDFTM technology for production of parts in aerospace industry.

Figure 1 shows the variation of the apparent moduli due to temperature change for LDFTM and continuous fiber systems (AS-4/PEKK) with off-axis specimens. Figure 2 shows the variation of the tensile strengths due to fiber orientation for off-axis specimens of the LDFTM and continuous fiber systems. It is concluded from these results that the elastic moduli and strengths of LDFTM AS-4/PEKK are equivalent to those of continuous fiber systems. When ambient temperature is increased, the moduli and strengths decrease. The amount of reduction is generally less for LDFTM system than for "continuous fiber" system.

The stress-strain curves of off-axis specimens for LDFTM and continuous fiber AS-4/PEKK at 24°C and 177°C are given in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. The theoretical stress-strain curves based on the one-parameter plasticity model are shown as solid lines superimposing the experimental points. Excellent agreement was observed between the theoretical curves and the experimental data for both LDFTM and continuous fiber systems at various temperatures.

3.2 Plasticity Model

The theoretical stress-strain curves were derived from the following relation based on the one-parameter plasticity model [8, 9]:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + \epsilon_x^p = \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + [h(\theta)]^{n+1} A \sigma_x^n$$

where E_x is the apparent elastic modulus; σ_x is the applied stress, ϵ_x^p is the effective plastic strain, θ is the off-axis angle. The coefficients A and n were determined by linear regression of the logarithmic values from the following relation between the effective stress $\bar{\sigma}$ and the effective plastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ which can be established based on off-axis loading test results:

$$\bar{\epsilon}^p = A \left(\bar{\sigma} \right)^n$$

4. MECHANICAL PROPERTY PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITES

4.1 Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composites

4.1.1 Tensile, Compressive, Flexural and Shear Properties

Static mechanical properties of LDF™ and continuous fiber AS-4/PEKK (58% fiber volume) including tensile, compressive, flexural and shear strengths are summarized in Table 1. While the unidirectional (0°) moduli and strengths of LDF™ composites are slightly lower than its counterparts of continuous fiber composites, the transverse tensile moduli and strengths of LDF™ system are greater than the continuous fiber counterparts. These results suggest that the LDF™ fiber alignment contains slightly more off axis fibers than the continuous fiber system. Yet, basic lamina stiffness parameters and strength values of the LDF™ system still compare favorably with current state-of-the-art aerospace epoxy systems and other high performance thermoplastic composites.

An early concern of the LDF™ material system was what happened to the performance of the material after it has been drawn. Strength and stiffness measurements of an 8 ply unidirectional LDF™ AS-4/PEKK laminate drawn to various degrees of elongation showed no significant change in allowable stress or modulus after forming (Fig. 5) [10].

TABLE 1

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AS-4/PEKK

<u>PROPERTY</u>		<u>LDF™</u>	<u>CONTINUOUS</u>
Tensile			
Strength (0°)	MPa	1615	1677
Modulus (0°)	GPa	123.5	129.6
Strength (90°)	MPa	91	73
Modulus (90°)	GPa	10.3	8.3
Compressive			
Strength (0°)	MPa	1263	1394
Modulus (0°)	GPa	110.4	121.4
Flexural			
Strength (0°)	MPa	1656	1932
Modulus (0°)	GPa	124.1	127.5
Shear			
Inplane Strength	MPa	146	142
Inplane Modulus	GPa	5.5	5.5
Short Beam Strength	MPa	110	117

4.1.2 Damage Tolerance and Toughness

The damage tolerance and toughness properties of LDF™ and continuous fiber AS-4/PEKK (58% fiber volume) were evaluated by open hole tension and open hole compression tests at room temperature or under hot-wet conditions as given in Table 2 [6]. Both material systems have nearly equivalent damage tolerance and hot-wet properties. This was confirmed by compression-after-impact test with both LDF™ and continuous fiber systems yielding 273 MPa strength and 0.6% strain to failure after impact with 67 J/cm (1500 in-lb/in). High interlaminar toughness (G_{1c}) at 1.4 KJ/m² was obtained by Double Cantilever Beam Test for both material systems.

TABLE 2

DAMAGE TOLERANCE AND TOUGHNESS OF AS-4/PEKK

<u>Property</u>		<u>Temperature</u>	<u>LDF™</u>	<u>Continuous</u>
Open Hole Tension	MPa	25°C	318	335
	MPa	82°C Wet	305	311
	MPa	121°C Wet	313	318
Open Hole Compression	MPa	25°C	307	326
	MPa	82°C Wet	282	284
	MPa	121°C Wet	257	273
Compression After Impact	MPa	25°C	40	40
	%		0.6	0.6
Interlaminar Fracture Toughness	KJ/M ²	25°C	1.4	1.4

4.1.3 Creep and Fatigue Performance

The time-dependent creep performance of LDF™ AS-4/PEKK versus its "continuous" fiber reinforced counterpart was evaluated at elevated temperature 82°C (180°F), using specimens with quasi-isotropic layup (0, 90, ±45) and 25 cm x 3.8 cm x 0.25 cm dimensions. The tensile creep test was run with 80% load and 10,000 minutes duration.

The test results showed that LDF™ AS-4/PEKK composites are equivalent to AS-4/PEKK "continuous" fiber composites in tensile creep at 82°C (180°F), both with insignificant increase (0.016×10^{-6} cm/cm/minute) in tensile strain at 80% load over 10,000 minutes after initial induction period of approximately 60 minutes. Thus, no adverse effect of discontinuous fiber ends was observed for the LDF™ AS-4/PEKK specimens. A plot of strain (%) vs. time (minutes) from creep test results with specimens of AS-4/3501-6 epoxy, LDF™ or continuous AS-4/PEKK is shown in Figure 6.

Similar results were obtained at Du Pont with dead weight tensile loading of $[\pm 45]_S$ specimens of both continuous and LDF™ AS-4/PEKK composites used to evaluate the shear induced room temperature creep performance with fiber-matrix interaction as a predominant factor [11].

Initial creep test at the Composite Materials Laboratory of Purdue University showed no creep strain for the unidirectional (0°) specimens of LDF™ AS-4/PEKK with 70-80% tension load at room temperature or 121°C over 24 hours [12].

The long term durability in fatigue of both continuous fiber and LDF™ AS-4/PEKK composites has been found good and compared well with observed performance of other thermoplastics and epoxy matrix composites. The flex fatigue performance of LDF™ AS-4/PEKK is equivalent to that of the continuous fiber composites. The fatigue data with considerable scattering are shown in Figure 7 [11].

4.1.4 Thermal Properties

Thermal properties of LDF™ system with semi-crystalline PEKK matrix such as crystallinity, crystallization kinetics, thermal expansion, thermal conductivity and heat capacity were characterized and reported [13]. These properties are relevant in thermoforming to achieve optimum mechanical performance of the LDF™ or continuous fiber reinforced composite parts. It has been found that the semi-crystalline PEKK matrix system with optimal thermal properties is adaptable for thermoforming LDF™ composite parts. Relevant thermal properties of LDF™ or continuous AS-4/PEKK composites are summarized in Table 3.

TABLE 3

THERMAL PROPERTIES OF AS-4/PEKK COMPOSITES

<u>THERMAL PROPERTIES</u>	<u>LDF™</u>	<u>CONTINUOUS</u>
Glass Transition Temperature, °C	156	156
Processing Temperature, °C	360-370	360-370
Optimum Crystallization Temp., °C	255	255
Crystallization peak Time, min.	0.1	0.1
Matrix Crystallinity, %	26	26
Thermal Expansion Coefficient, m/m°C		
In Plane, 30 - 250°C	3X10 ⁻⁶	3X10 ⁻⁶
Out of Plane, 30-150°C	41X10 ⁻⁶	44X10 ⁻⁶
150-250°C	131X10 ⁻⁶	145X10 ⁻⁶
Thermal Conductivity (60-213°C) W/mK	0.6-0.7	0.3-0.5
Heat Capacity (60-400°C) KJ/KgK	0.9-1.7	0.9-1.7

5. TECHNOLOGY DEMONSTRATION FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATION5.1 Background

A development program was initiated in 1988 by Bell Helicopter Textron, Incorporated to evaluate the design, manufacture and performance of a "one-piece" thermoplastic wing rib for V-22 tiltrotor aircraft. The existing wing ribs, fabricated from carbon/epoxy thermoset materials, use five stiffeners and two cords attached to the rib web by approximately 150 mechanical fasteners (Figure 8). This program was aimed to reduce aircraft weight (by 50%) and cost (by 65%) via designing a "one-piece" wing rib (Figure 9). Consequently, Du Pont's LDF™ AS-4/PEKK, BASF's commingled fabric and ICI's APC-2 with continuous AS-4/PEEK were selected as the candidate materials for the thermoplastic wing rib [14].

5.2 Material Property Performance

Tension, compression and shear specimens of the candidate materials including LDF™ AS-4/PEKK (58% fiber volume) were fabricated and tested to establish the required preliminary design allowables for structural application. The test data at Bell Helicopter Textron showed that both LDF™ AS-4/PEKK and APC-2 allowables have exceeded the design requirements at the critical loading conditions for open-hole compression at 82°C (180°F)/wet.

Both LDF™AS-4/PEKK and APC-2 also showed excellent environmental resistance in aerospace fluids such as jet fuel, hydraulic fluid, MEK and de-icing agent with more than 90% retention of the initial property after exposure [14].

5.3 Manufacturing Process

Due to processibility and formability of LDF™ system in manufacture of complex-shaped parts, Du Pont used female steel tool and matched die press forming process as opposed to the diaphragm forming process used by ICI for APC-2 to fabricate the wing rib components. The preplied LDF™ sheet was heated in an infrared oven to a surface temperature of 390°C, then quickly transferred into the preheated dies. The periphery of the sheet was clamped during the forming by a hydraulic clamp system to prevent wrinkling. Three wing rib doors and webs were successfully fabricated by Du Pont and delivered to Bell Helicopter for structural testing.

5.4 Characterization By Thermal Analysis

The skin specimens of a thermoplastic wing rib manufactured with thermoformable LDF™ AS-4/PEKK sheet were characterized by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The thermoplastic wing rib skin clearly exhibits crystalline characteristic with melting peak at 336°C and crystallization peak at 265°C. Crystallinity of PEKK matrix in the composite part is approximately 25% as estimated from the heat of fusion (11 J/g) with adjustment of 34% matrix weight. This level of crystallinity was sufficient for AS-4/PEKK composites to provide resistance to aerospace fluids.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed for the same wing rib skin from room temperature up to 300°C. The LDF™ composite skin with nominal 58% fiber volume provided high flexural modulus of 18 GPa at room temperature, 17 GPa at 154°C and 11 GPa at 190°C which is a glass transition for AS-4/PEKK composites as determined by DMA.

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

LDF™ technology combined with PEKK offers potential in cost reduction for complex shaped parts manufacture. The mechanical property performance of LDF™ systems with AS-4/PEKK has been demonstrated. The LDF™ system is equivalent to the continuous fiber counter part in static or dynamic (creep, fatigue) mechanical properties. No adverse effect of discontinuous fiber ends has been observed in the property performance.

These results are in agreement with the fundamental theory on stress transfer for "aligned" long discontinued fiber in LDF™ system.

The LDF™ technology was demonstrated via "parts" fabrication such as tiltrotor aircraft wing ribs in cooperation with Bell Helicopter Textron, Incorporated. LDF™ AS-4/PEKK is superior to the baseline epoxy based system in open-hole compression design allowable and has exceeded the design requirements at the critical loading conditions.

7. REFERENCES

1. C. W. Schneider and A. M. James, 35th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, CA, April 2-5, 1990 (Closed Session), pp. 56-68.
2. R. K. Okine, D. H. Edison and N. K. Little, 32nd International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, CA, April 6-9, 1987, pp. 1413-1425.
3. R. K. Okine, 20th International SAMPE Technical Conference, pp. 148-161 (1988).
4. I. Y. Chang, 33rd International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, CA, March 7-10, 1988, pp. 194-205.
5. B. D. Agarwal and L. J. Broutman, Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., (1980), Chapter 3, pp. 71-103.
6. J. F. Pratte, W. H. Krueger and I. Y. Chang, 34th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Reno, NV, May 8-11, 1989, pp. 2229-2242.
7. S. Khan, J. F. Pratte, I. Y. Chang and W. H. Krueger, 35th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, CA, April 2-5, 1990, pp. 1579-1593.
8. C. T. Sun, I. Chung and I. Y. Chang, Fifth Technical Conference, the American Society for Composites, East Lansing, MI, June 12-14, 1990, pp. 1011-1020.
9. C. T. Sun and J. L. Chen, the Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials, Imperial College, London, England, July 20-25, 1987, pp. 1250-1259.
10. A. P. Perrella, 21st International SAMPE Technical Conference, Atlantic City, NJ, September 25-28, 1989, pp. 705-719.
11. R. B. Croman (Du Pont), Personal Communication.
12. C. T. Sun (Purdue University), Personal Communication.
13. I. Y. Chang and B. S. Hsiao, 36th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, San Diego, CA, April 15-18, 1991.
14. E. J. Shahwan, Fabricating Composites'90 (EM90-665), Arlington, TX, October 8-11, 1990.

Figure 1: Modulus vs. temperature plot with various fiber orientation

Figure 2: Strength vs. fiber orientation at 24°C and 177°C

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves at 24°C

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves at 177°C

Figure 5: Post-formed LDF™ strength/ stiffness retention

Figure 6: Tensile creep of composites

Figure 7: Flex fatigue of composites

Figure 8: Thermoset wing rib

Figure 9: Thermoplastic wing rib